

A SIMPLE METHOD FOR SEPARATING HOMONYMS AND POLYSEMY

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ABSTRACT

It can be very challenging to tell the difference between homonymy and polysemy in English. This article discusses simple methods for distinguishing between them. Homonymy and polysemy appear to be the same thing at first glance. But every speaker and learner of a language must make a distinction between the two.

The primary distinction between the two is that although in polysemy the senses are related, in homonymy they are not. Now that they are significantly different. Homonymy senses now have a connection. What then is connected? Homonymy may be based on easy similarities in sound or orthography. Orthography is simply the use of letters or spelling. Thus, the word for writing is orthography. What happens if we have two words that have completely unrelated semantic meanings yet sound identical?

Homophone is interesting and it sounds easy because you just say "homo" - same, "phone" - sound. Homophones means words that share the same sound although they have different meaning and different spelling. For example the words: **two & too, see & sea, meat & meet, bear & bare**. Homophony can be more complicated two words are homophones if they have identical pronunciation. But why do we have homophony in the first place? Why do not we try to pronounce everything different **tail and tale**. So if you want to pronounce tail and tale when we have to pronounce to tail as dial maybe and then tail and tale are two different words. Basically, they are totally different and they mean different things. But they have come to sound similar usually in case of the homophone.

Tale (noun) - a story about exciting imaginary events.

Tail (noun) - the part that sticks out at the back of an animal body and that it can move.

The 2 words used to sound different but because of changes into language, they have come to sound the same. But they are changes in phonology, which is an integral part of language because language looks like a living organism. It grows, changes and it even dies like a plant. Thus language changes and then words that did not sound the same may come to sound the same. But if you think about this, you know considering that potentially we have a limited number of sounds in language. But there is an informative number of things to talk about in other words. Meaning is unlimited, but language sound are limited. It would only make sense to try to economize on linguistic form. So in that sense, it would only make sense to have at

least some degree homophony language. Because we can use the same to refer to different things. So it looks like a smart thing. You might say would not that be confusing if you look at carefully. For example, the word *bear* (*noun*) and *bear* (*verb*). Although the sounds are the same. We already knows they belong two different stylistic categories. One of them is a noun, one of them is a verb. Then we know that they are going to be used differently in the sentences. So we do not usually you only use a single word. We do not say bear, they usually use it in a sentences or phrase. The context will clarify whether it is bear the noun or the bear is the verb. It puts language in perspective. Therefore, for example, when we talk about bear the noun, we know that it has a different form. Bears as plural, we know that bears the verb has a past tense and past participle: bore - born, bears (singular). Third person singular bears people can distinguish the differences in context. So context is very important, it helps us clarify the word. First, in rapid communication a homophony is very efficient in the sense that as long as it is not confusing, it can save us language forms. But then if it is a confusing we can clarify. Even if people use the word bear in their speech, that time it is easy to know which is an animal or which is a verb form.

Polysemy which means when there is more than one meaning involved and the context does not make clear. What meaning is being referred to. For instance, I found a fascinating table.

Table here could in the sense that could be a piece of furniture or it could be a table of figures in a book.

Polysemy the words are related. But in a homophony are naturally. For example, the words plain in English polysemous. The same word means clear, unadorned, obvious. So that you have the word plain which is one word and it means different things. How do you know what it means? We can look at the context. for instance, that means it does not make it complicated. But if a girl says I play in wooden table here, it means unadorned, without much decoration and stuff and in plain sight means it is easy to see or notice, especially when it should be hidden. Polysemy and homophony are dealing with different meaning. But polysemy it is one word in homophones are two or more words. Homophony and polysemy can be compared in the sense that multiple meaning are involved. Next one is homography, there are words that share the same spelling, but different meaning and sometimes different sound, such as **live - live, bow - bow**. Homonyms are words that share the same spelling and the same sound, but different meaning. For example, **what - watch, bat - bat**.

Bank (money) - people can have to do with money

Bank (river) - can have to do with river.

These words are pronounced the same and their orthography is exactly the same. It is called a case of homonymy. How about case where the sounds are the same. But the orthography is different when take the word ring and the word ring and notice that the senses first of all the unrelated ring here means to twist something until it extracts all these water that is in it. While ring here is something you wear on your finger. This sound is exactly the same, the orthography is different, for example, house as a noun and house as a verbs. The orthography or the way the work is written is exactly the same. The senses are unrelated house is a place, house is an action, the sounds are differ. Such as, *house* is pronounced **s** as a *noun*, and **z** as a *verb*.

1st picture

A word that has a linked meaning in different aspects. For example, a word is **head** - it can be the head of a person or it can be the **head** of a department. Also a word is **foot**, it can be foot of a person or the **foot** of a mountain. So this is called polysemy. Polysemy is a word that has a linked meaning in different aspects.

To conclude, homophones are words that shares the same sound, but they have different spelling and different meaning. Such as see and sea. Homography are words that share the same written form them, but they have different sound and they have different meaning, live and live. homonyms are words that share the same spelling and the same pronunciation or sound, but they have different meaning watch and watch. Polysemy is a word that has linked meaning in different ways, food of a person or foot of the mountain.

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